

**SPECIFIC ASPECTS REGARDING THE TESTING OF FLAMEPROOF
ENCLOSURE EQUIPMENT INTENDED FOR USE IN HAZARDOUS AREAS
ENDANGERED BY THE PRESENCE OF HYDROGEN**

Sc.res. I PhD Eng. Lucian Moldovan¹

Sc.res. I PhD Eng. Adrian Jurca¹

Sc.res. I PhD Eng. Mihai Magyari¹

Sc.res. III PhD Eng. Marcel Rad¹

Sc.res. assist. Eng. Valentin Sîrbu¹

¹ National Institute for Research and Development INSEMEX Petrosani, **Romania**

ABSTRACT

The type of protection flameproof enclosure consists in placing the parts that can ignite an explosive atmosphere into an enclosure that can withstand an internal explosion and it prevents the transmission of the explosion effects (hot gases, flames, incandescent particles etc.) capable of ignition to the external explosive atmosphere in which the equipment is placed.

The purpose of the paper is to underline some specific situations that can occur during the tests in explosive mixtures needed to verify the characteristics ensuring explosion protection in case of flameproof enclosure “d” type of protection. When speaking of enclosures having regular geometrical shapes and normal internal distribution of components the pressures and pressure curves exhibit a normal behavior. But, when the enclosure has an internal distribution of components that leads to pressure peaks and pre-compression phenomena during an internal explosion the results will present a different behavior. The tests in explosive mixture will be performed to a specific flameproof enclosure according to the testing methodology presented in the standard EN 60079-1 with explosive mixtures of hydrogen-air and acetylene-air. The obtained results of the tests, will be compared to show some specific particular aspects related to the tests in explosive mixtures, especially regarding the maximum explosion pressure.

Keywords: Flameproof enclosure, hydrogen, tests, internal explosion, explosion pressure

INTRODUCTION

Equipment protected to explosion by the type of protection flameproof enclosure “d” are considered, generally, equipment that can produce electrical arcs and sparks in normal operation and the parts considered to be an ignition source are placed inside of an enclosure, constructed so as to resist the explosion pressure (developed during an internal explosion) of an explosive mixture, also preventing the transmission of the explosion effects to the explosive atmosphere surrounding the enclosure [6], [10]. The requirements for assessing flameproof enclosure equipment are described in SR EN IEC 60079-0 and SR EN 60079-1 [1], [8], [10].

The flameproof enclosure “d” type of protection presents specific elements called flameproof joints [3], [6], [10]. The flameproof joints can be threaded, non-treaded or